

INTERFACIAL ADHESION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BAMBOO FIBRE COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *fibre-matrix adhesion, wetting, natural fibre composites, bamboo fibre*

1 Introduction

Bamboo fibres have recently attracted interest as a sustainable reinforcement fibre in (polymer) composite materials due to specific mechanical properties which are comparable to glass fibres. Low cost, environmental friendliness and natural abundance make such fibres possible substitutes to synthetic reinforcing fibre materials, especially for polymer matrix composites.

To achieve good wetting and adhesion of the bamboo fibre with different polymers, the fibre surface needs to be characterized. However, natural fibres have several complex characteristics such as liquid sorption, different cross sections along the fibre length, chemical heterogeneity, which make obtaining meaningful data from wetting measurements particularly challenging. Therefore, the interpretation of their wetting behaviour as quasi-equilibrium phenomena can be invalid.

Bonding between the reinforcing fibre and the matrix has a significant effect on the properties of the composite since stress transfer and load distribution efficiency at the interface is determined by the degree of adhesion between the components. Using the experimental data obtained from wetting measurements, fibres and matrices can be examined and matched in terms of their surface energy components; predicting and verifying their compatibility allows more suitable combinations and therefore better composites to be made.

In this study, a novel procedure based on an autoclave treatment is presented, allowing stable and reproducible advancing contact angles to be measured. The wetting behaviour of bamboo fibres and thermoplastic matrices (polyvinylidene fluoride PVDF and grafted maleic anhydride polypropylene MAPP) is characterized through the Wilhelmy

technique, the molecular-kinetic theory of wetting is used to interpret the contact angle experimental data, the fibre surface is characterized by AFM and XPS. Surface energy components of bamboo fibres and thermoplastic matrices are estimated by using the acid-base approach. Furthermore, the surface of the bamboo is altered in order to change the surface energy components using a chitosan coating treatment. Additionally, unidirectional bamboo fibre composites are prepared in order to obtain a direct measure of the effect of physical adhesion by performing 3-point bending tests (transverse and longitudinally).

2 Results and discussion

2.1 Wetting behaviour

In the case of natural fibres, a direct measurement of the contact angle is problematic, and so their wetting behaviour is difficult to study. The Wilhelmy technique represents a reliable method to study the wetting behaviour of bamboo fibres at different immersion speeds [1]. We could prove that by using autoclave treatment we could minimize surface waviness, roughness and liquid penetration, without changing surface chemistry. Thus the bamboo fibre surface represented a well defined system and so its wetting behaviour can be studied and a meaningful interpretation of wetting data is ensured (Fig. 1).

For this to be the case, contact angles of bamboo fibres must show an expected dependence to immersion velocity. The molecular-kinetic theory [2,3] provides a reasonable fit to the data, confirming the expected immersion velocity dependency, reproducibility and stability of the advancing contact angle in a bamboo-water system; indicating that the measured contact angle is the true advancing contact angle (Fig. 2).

Fig.1. Advancing contact angle for autoclaved and non-autoclaved bamboo fibres in water.

Fig.2. Dynamic contact angle as a function of wetting velocity for water on bamboo technical fibre, according to the molecular kinetic theory. The theoretical curve through the data was obtained by nonlinear regression of experimental data.

2.2 Surface chemical composition

Figure 3 shows the results regarding surface chemical constituents of both autoclave-treated and non-treated technical bamboo fibres obtained from the decomposition of the high resolution carbon 1s spectrum for each fibre. Lignin content on the fibre surface was analyzed by determining the oxygen-to-carbon atomic ratio, and the relative concentration of the C1 component. The results clearly indicate that technical bamboo surface constituents are close to our references for lignin, indicating that bamboo technical fibres may be homogeneously covered with lignin and possibly some other molecules, but not with cellulose. On autoclave treatment, the surface chemistry does not change.

O/C vs C1/C

Fig.3. C1/C ratios versus O/C ratios for chemical groups at the surface of bamboo fibres. Theoretical values for cellulose and lignin according to Shchukarev [4].

2.3 Surface energy components and work of adhesion

Once the advancing contact angles of the liquids have been obtained, the surface tension components can be determined. According to the acid-base theory, the total surface tension of the bamboo fibres was estimated to be $39,1 \pm 2$ mN/m, with an acid and base contribution of 0,3 mN/m and 10 mN/m respectively (see table 2). Accordingly, the fibre’s surface is relatively hydrophobic and a Lewis base, this means that a strong acidic Lewis matrix could give the best adhesion performance. So for optimal physical adhesion, the surface energy of the substrate should be as high as possible, while the two phases have the same Lifshitz-van der Waals components and the acidic component of the substrate is equal to the basic component of the liquid and vice versa [5,6].

The measured advancing contact angles (0,15 mm/min) and the there from calculated surface tension components¹ can be seen in table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1. The advancing contact angles of treated bamboo fibre and thermoplastics measured with water, formamide, ethylene glycol, methylene iodide and glycerol.

	W	FORM	EG	MI	GLYC
bamboo	69±3,2	X	43±3,7	47±2,9	X
chit	108±9,1	79±4,7	64±5,8	X	X
PVDF	73±0,2	58±0,3	X	X	72±0,7
PP	82±1,3	72±1,3	61±1,9	59±1,9	X
MAPP	78±2,0	75±1,6	65±1,4	60±2,2	X

¹ SurfTen 4.3, a program for the calculation of acid-base solid surface free energy components by Claudio Della Volpe

TABLE 2. Surface tension components of the treated and untreated bamboo fibres and thermoplastics.

	$\gamma(\frac{mN}{m})$	$\gamma^{LW}(\frac{mN}{m})$	$\gamma^+(\frac{mN}{m})$	$\gamma^-(\frac{mN}{m})$
bamboo	39,1	35,9	0,3	10,0
chitosan	45,0	44,1	0,2	1,1
PVDF	27,1	7,4	48,4	2,0
PP	29,9	28,7	0,1	3,2
MAPP	28,1	27,6	0,0	5,1

As expected, PVDF has a very low LW component. This is due to London dispersion force reduction, present in most fluorocarbons like PVDF and Teflon. As the high electronegativity of fluorine reduces the polarizability of the atom, fluorocarbons are only weakly susceptible to the fleeting dipoles that form the basis of the London dispersion force. As a result, fluorocarbons have low intramolecular attractive forces and are lipophobic in addition to being hydrophobic/nonpolar [7].

The high electronegativity of fluorine is also responsible for the high + value of PVDF. The net force on a molecule is an electron drawing force, from all sides, keeping one another in balance in the bulk.

The work of physical adhesion is calculated for the different materials by using equation 1 with bamboo as the substrate.

$$W_a = \gamma_l + \gamma_s - \gamma_{sl} \quad (1)$$

where γ_l is the liquid surface tension, γ_s is the solid surface energy and γ_{sl} is the interfacial energy. The following values for W_a were obtained: 78 mN/m for PVDF, 66 mN/m for MAPP and 68 mN/m for PP.

Fig.4. Transversal properties of MAPP, PP and PVDF bamboo composites at different processing temperatures.

Looking at these results one would expect really good results when using PVDF and more or less the same results for PP and MAPP. It has to be noted that these values only relate to intramolecular forces and do not relate to covalent bonding.

Fig.5. Longitudinal properties of MAPP, PP and PVDF bamboo composites at different processing temperatures.

Figure 4 and 5 show the transversal and longitudinal properties of MAPP, PP and PVDF bamboo composites made with the same procedure either at 175 °C or 200 °C and with a volume fraction of 40%.

The calculated values for the work of adhesion correlate reasonably well with the obtained results for the transversal properties, shown in figure 4, except for PP200. As predicted by the calculated work of adhesion our results for PVDF are better than the others (once the PVDF is properly molten at 200°C). Proving that the work of adhesion has really improved.

2.4 Bamboo fibre surface treatments

Bamboo fibres and prepreps were coated with chitosan using an aqueous Chitosan-CO₂ solution [8].

The main idea of this treatment is to cover the surface with chitosan, increasing the amount of available hydroxyl-groups on the surface. In this way, the properties of MAPP-bamboo composites might be increased, since lignin has fewer hydroxyl-groups at the surface, and MAPP has the capability to form covalent bonds with hydroxyl groups through esterification.

The obtained results in tables 1 and 2 for MAPP are very similar to the results obtained for PP. The small differences in values are created by the presence of the maleic anhydride in MAPP.

The change is relatively small because we worked with a 1wt% MAPP. Calculating the work of adhesion with chitosan as the substrate (72 mN/m for MAPP), we see that this has increased for the chitosan coated fibre. So theoretically we would expect better properties with chitosan coated bamboo. Looking at figures 6 and 7 we only see this improvement in the longitudinal direction. We have an increase of 22% for the longitudinal strength while the transversal shows a decrease of 18%. This means that we are not really improving the adhesion strength, possibly because of lower transverse strength of the chitosan coating. Further tests need to be carried out to evaluate this hypothesis.

The calculated work of adhesion for PVDF with chitosan coated bamboo (52 mN/m) is much smaller than for PVDF with untreated bamboo (78 mN/m). So theoretically one would expect a composite made with bamboo and PVDF to be much stronger than a composite made with chitosan coated bamboo and PVDF. The results of the three point bending correspond with the theory and are shown in figures 6 and 7.

Fig.6. Longitudinal properties of chitosan coated and uncoated, MAPP and PVDF bamboo composites.

The composite with the uncoated fibre is about 28% stronger in the longitudinal direction and about 300% better in the transversal. Showing that the adhesion is better in the uncoated fibre. Both composites show about the same longitudinal

stiffness, which is around 80% of the theoretical value of 19,2 GPa according to the rule of mixtures, indicating similar levels of wetting.

Fig.7. Transversal properties of chitosan coated and uncoated, MAPP and PVDF bamboo composites.

3 Conclusions

The high concentration of lignin on the surface of technical bamboo fibres, as concluded from XPS results, seems to be responsible for their wetting properties. Autoclave treatment was used to smoothen the lignin surface layer.

The wetting behaviour of bamboo fibres appears to conform well to the predictions of the molecular-kinetic theory. Therefore, it was possible to obtain experimental wetting data on bamboo fibres with reasonable accuracy, allowing meaningful information on interfacial interactions to be deduced. In this way, surface components of bamboo fibres and thermoplastic matrices were matched, resulting in the improvement of the physical adhesion of bamboo fibre composites revealed by 3-point bending test results. Accordingly, the properties of PVDF lend themselves well for the preparation of bamboo composites with high interface strength.

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